

Automatic skin layer segmentation and 3D volume reconstruction from OCT images

James R.E. Hall¹ and Hannes P. Saal¹

¹ Active Touch Lab, Department of Psychology, University of Sheffield, Sheffield, UK

Abstract. Understanding the microstructure and mechanical behavior of the skin requires highly detailed three-dimensional measurements of skin morphology *in vivo*. Here we present a tool to automatically and accurately segment the stratum corneum from Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) images of glabrous skin and generate 3D volumes from image stacks. The resulting reconstructions generalize across different skin sites (hand and foot) and are robust to deformation of the skin, allowing future study of mechanical properties of the skin.

Keywords: Optical Coherence Tomography

1 Introduction

Many questions about the skin's microstructure and how it deforms remain unanswered [1][2] due to the lack of three-dimensional high-resolution in-vivo structural imaging. Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) is a common in-vivo imaging technique used to investigate skin structure due to its relative ease of use and its ability to clearly delineate the layers of the skin. However, OCT is most commonly employed in 2D, as interpreting raw 3D data is difficult due to the noisy nature of the acquired images. Thus, a 3D volume created directly from an image stack can be difficult to understand and much harder to analyze, with small structures in the skin being obscured. To address this problem, previous studies have used segmentation models to generate surface meshes for the layers of the skin, most often the stratum corneum [3]. However, the models used to segment these images are often proprietary; they are commonly trained for clinical purposes on specific datasets for skin with defects, they also do not offer sufficient spatial resolution for investigations into the microstructure of the skin at scales of tens of micrometers and are only usable on undeformed skin. In order to mitigate these problems, we designed a tool to automatically generate high-resolution point clouds for skin layers in glabrous skin from OCT images. Unlike previous attempts our model aims to also be generic and applicable to multiple skin sites and contact conditions.

Fig. 1. Process of generating 3D models of the stratum corneum in glabrous skin. (a) The raw data is extracted into separate frames as PNG images. (b) Post-processing on the individual images. (c) Pre-trained Unet++ [4] with a resnet152 encoder is used to automatically segment the stratum corneum. (d) The segmentation generates binary masks of the stratum corneum. (e) The masks are combined into a point cloud to create a 3D model of the stratum corneum.

2 Materials and methods

Data collection was approved by the ethical review board of the Department of Psychology at the University of Sheffield. Data was collected using a clinically approved Vivosight OCT system (Michelson Diagnostics). 3D scans of glabrous skin were obtained both with the skin patch directly beneath the scanner head and with a deforming plate against the skin. Data was collected from 8 participants and from 6 skin sites on the hand and the sole of the foot to train a generic segmentation model usable for all types of glabrous skin. The stimuli used to deform the finger were transparent and contained a variety of curved features in their surface to deform the skin, allowing us to train the model on skin under a variety of conditions to avoid overfitting to a specific skin structure. The current model concerns segmentation of the top skin layer, the stratum corneum, while work on deeper layers is ongoing.

The model works as follows (see Fig. 1): first, the raw frames from the scan are extracted from the original data file. Each slice extracted from the scan is split into 4 images at different focal depths; next, the raw images are post-processed with the 4 components of each image combined into one image. A wavelet-FFT filter [5] is used to remove stripe artifacts from the images. The images are then segmented by a Unet++ network with a resnet152 encoder which was trained on 240 manually segmented OCT images. Segmentation produces a series of binary masks delineating the skin layer. Finally, points are created along the boundary of each segmented image and when combined create a 3D point cloud.

Fig. 2. 3D volumes of the stratum corneum generated using our model. (a) A region of skin from the fingertip. (b) Palm of the hand. (c) Medial metatarsal sole of the foot.

3 Preliminary results and future work

Our segmentation model and image processing methods allow for accurate segmentation of the stratum corneum in the glabrous skin of the hand and foot (see Fig. 2). Our model achieved a 0.9 dice score during training on augmented data showing its accuracy. Structurally relevant features and their differences between skin regions are evident, such as the ticker stratum corneum at the foot sole and subtle differences in the ridge structure between all three skin sites. Moreover, small features such as sweat glands are readily observable. This could be used to answer questions about the 3D morphology of the skin as well as testing dynamic behavior of the skin in 3D. To make analysis of skin layers in 3D as simple as possible we have developed a software package which allows the user to import raw data files and automatically segment the slices and create a volume from the results. Our future plan is to extend the model to cover deeper layers, such as the viable epidermis, and potentially collagen fibers. We will also share the software package with other researchers.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare.

References

1. Cauna, N.: Nature and functions of the papillary ridges of the digital skin. *The Anatomical Record* **119**(4), 449–468 (1954)
2. Giulia Corniani, Lee, Z. S., Carré, M. J., Lewis, R., Delhayé, B. P., & Saal, H. P.: Sub-surface deformation of individual fingerprint ridges during tactile interactions. *ELife* (2024)
3. Sciolla, B., Jimmy Le Digabel, Gwendal Josse, Thibaut Dambry, Guibert, B. and Philippe Delachartre.: Joint segmentation and characterization of the dermis in 50 MHz ultrasound 2D and 3D images of the skin. *Computers in Biology and Medicine* **103** 277–286 (2018)
4. Zhou, Z., Rahman Siddiquee, M. M., Tajbakhsh, N., & Liang, J.: UNet++: A Nested U-Net Architecture for Medical Image Segmentation. *Deep Learning in Medical Image Analysis and Multimodal Learning for Clinical Decision Support*, 3–11 (2018)
5. Byers, R., & Matcher, S.: Attenuation of stripe artifacts in optical coherence tomography images through wavelet-FFT filtering. *Biomedical Optics Express* **10**(8), 4179 (2019)